

Supplementary Methods for “Fast Effect Size Shrinkage Software for Beta-Binomial Models of Allelic Imbalance”

Model Setup

For the g -th gene ($1 \leq g \leq G$), a beta-binomial GLM was fit to model ASRe counts as follows. Let Y_{ig} be the read counts of the first of the two alleles (which allele is designated as the first allele is arbitrary) for the i -th subject, $1 \leq i \leq I$. Investigators may designate the first and second alleles of a gene as the paternal and maternal alleles or as the alternate and reference alleles. It is assumed that $Y_{ig} \stackrel{ind}{\sim} \text{BetaBin}(n_{ig}, p_{ig}, \phi_g)$, where n_{ig} is equal to the total read counts (of both alleles) for the i -th subject, p_{ig} is the probability of reads belonging to the first allele for the i -th subject, and ϕ_g is the overdispersion parameter. The beta-binomial distribution models proportions that exhibit more variance than what would typically be observed under a binomial distribution, and this additional variance is called the overdispersion. In this case, $E(Y_{ig}) = n_{ig}p_{ig}$ and $\text{Var}(Y_{ig}) = \frac{n_{ig}p_{ig}(1-p_{ig})(1+(n_{ig}-1)\frac{1}{\phi_g+1})}{n_{ig}}$. Thus the overdispersion parameter ϕ_g is inversely related to the actual overdispersion, and $\phi_g \rightarrow \infty$ implies no more variance than what would be seen under a binomial distribution. n_{1g}, \dots, n_{Ig} are assumed to be fixed and known. As the beta-binomial probability mass function has multiple forms and parameterizations, we specify our parametrization below:

$$f(y_{ig}; n_{ig}, p_{ig}, \phi_g) = \frac{\binom{n_{ig}}{y_{ig}} B(y_{ig} + \phi_g p, n_{ig} - y_{ig} + \phi_g(1 - p_{ig}))}{B(\phi_g p_{ig}, \phi_g(1 - p_{ig}))} \quad (1)$$

where B specifies the beta function. Furthermore, let \mathbf{x}_i^T be the i -th row of our design matrix $\mathbf{X}_{I \times K}$, (matrix where the K columns are predictors of interest measured for each of the I samples). Potential predictors include disease status for association studies, parent of origin for imprinting studies, and the presence of an SNP for eQTL linkage studies. We also assume that $p_{ig} = [1 + \exp(-\mathbf{x}_i^T \boldsymbol{\beta}_g)]^{-1}$, or equivalently $\text{logit}(p_{ig}) = \mathbf{x}_i^T \boldsymbol{\beta}_g$, where $\boldsymbol{\beta}_g = (\beta_{1g}, \dots, \beta_{Kg})^T$ is a vector of coefficients representing the effect sizes for the predictors in our design matrix.

Apeglm additionally assumes a zero-centered Cauchy prior distribution for the effects of one of the predictors (Zhu, Ibrahim and Love 2018). Apeglm only shrinks the effect of one chosen predictor at a time, across all genes. We will denote the predictor whose effect investigators wish to shrink as the j -th predictor, $1 \leq j \leq K$.

To recap, we have:

$$Y_{ig} | \boldsymbol{\beta}_g \stackrel{ind}{\sim} \text{BetaBin}(n_{ig}, p_{ig}, \phi_g), \text{ for all } 1 \leq i \leq I, 1 \leq g \leq G \quad (2)$$

$$p_{ig} = \frac{1}{1 + \exp(-\mathbf{x}_i^T \boldsymbol{\beta}_g)}, \text{ for all } 1 \leq i \leq I, 1 \leq g \leq G \quad (3)$$

$$\beta_{jg} \stackrel{iid}{\sim} \text{Cauchy}(0, \gamma_j), \text{ for some } 1 \leq j \leq K \text{ and all } 1 \leq g \leq G \quad (4)$$

ML estimation only assumes (2) and (3), and estimation of $\boldsymbol{\beta}_g$ by maximum likelihood gives us our ML estimates. Apeglm additionally assumes (4), and the posterior of $\boldsymbol{\beta}_g$ is the product of the above Cauchy prior and beta-binomial likelihood. That is, $\boldsymbol{\beta}_g | Y_{1g}, \dots, Y_{Ig} \sim \text{Cauchy}(0, \gamma_j) \times \prod_{i=1}^I \text{BetaBin}(n_{ig}, p_{ig}, \phi_g)$. Genes with lower expression, smaller numbers of heterozygous subjects and higher dispersion in allelic proportions will have flatter likelihoods, which will lead to the prior having more influence and shrinkage being greater. Furthermore, if the ML estimates are tightly clustered about zero, the estimated scale parameter of our

Cauchy prior will be smaller. This will lead to more peakedness in the prior and also cause shrinkage to be greater. The mode of the posterior gives us our apeglm estimates of β_g .

Estimation Procedure

For each gene g , we wish to fit the generalized linear model $\text{logit}(p_{ig}) = \mathbf{x}_i^T \beta_g$ where $Y_{ig} | \beta_g \sim \text{BetaBin}(n_{ig}, p_{ig}, \phi_g)$ and n_{1g}, \dots, n_{Ig} are treated as fixed and known. For apeglm estimation, we additionally introduce a penalization/shrinkage term for the j -th predictor by assuming $\beta_{jg} \sim \text{Cauchy}(0, \gamma_j)$, where j is chosen by the user. The scale parameter of the prior, γ_j , is estimated by pooling information across genes. Thus, there are two unknown parameters for the maximum-likelihood model, the regression coefficient vector β_g and the overdispersion nuisance parameter ϕ_g , and an additional scale hyper-parameter γ_j for the Cauchy prior of the apeglm model. As the ML (or apeglm) estimate of β_g depends on the true value of ϕ_g and the ML estimate of ϕ_g depends on the true value of β_g , we alternate between maximum likelihood estimation of these two parameters to estimate ϕ_g , and treat this ML estimate as the true value for obtaining our ML or apeglm estimate of β_g . Specifically, estimation is conducted in seven steps:

1. For each gene $1 \leq g \leq G$, calculate the MLE for β_g as $\hat{\beta}_g^{(1)}$ assuming $\phi_g = \phi_g^{(0)}$, where $\phi_g^{(0)}$ is some initial guess (default is 100)
2. For each gene $1 \leq g \leq G$, calculate the MLE for ϕ_g as $\hat{\phi}_g^{(1)}$ assuming $\hat{\beta} = \hat{\beta}_g^{(1)}$
3. For each gene $1 \leq g \leq G$, calculate the MLE for β_g as $\hat{\beta}_g^{(2)}$ assuming $\phi_g = \hat{\phi}_g^{(1)}$
4. For each gene $1 \leq g \leq G$, calculate the MLE for ϕ_g as $\hat{\phi}_g^{(2)}$ assuming $\hat{\beta} = \hat{\beta}_g^{(2)}$
5. For each gene $1 \leq g \leq G$, calculate the MLE for β_g as $\hat{\beta}_g^{(3)}$ assuming $\phi_g = \hat{\phi}_g^{(2)}$
6. For each $1 \leq g \leq G$, calculate the MLE for ϕ_g as $\hat{\phi}_g$ assuming $\beta_g = \hat{\beta}_g^{(3)}$. This is taken as our final estimate for the overdispersion parameter.
 - 6b. If estimation by apeglm is desired, calculate an empirical Bayes estimate for γ_j as $\hat{\gamma}_j$.
7. For each gene $1 \leq g \leq G$, calculate the apeglm estimate or MLE for β_g as $\hat{\beta}_g$ assuming $\phi_g = \hat{\phi}_g$ and (if apeglm estimation is desired) $\hat{\gamma}_j = \gamma_j$. This is taken as our final estimate of the regression coefficient vector.

Estimating Coefficients while Overdispersion is Fixed

The steps below relate to iteration steps 1, 3, 5 or 7 above and assume that overdispersion is fixed and known. If estimation is being conducted by apeglm, the scale hyper-parameter of the zero-centered Cauchy prior is also assumed fixed and known.

We first discuss the methodology for apeglm estimation. In addition to assuming (2), (3) and (4), we also assume that $\beta_{j'g} \sim N(0, \sigma^2)$ for all $j' \neq j$ when calculating estimates, where σ^2 is some large value (the default is 15^2). That is, we assume weakly informative normal priors for effect sizes of the predictors that apeglm does not shrink, following the behavior of the software packages `bayesglm` (Gelman et. al. 2008) and `DESeq2` (Love, Huber and Anders 2014). These priors do not make a difference except when the MLE is highly unstable due to near-separability of the data or very weak information. In these rare cases, the wide normal priors allow for more numerically stable estimates and normally give more reliable solutions with lower generalization error. We discuss the effect of this prior more later on.

For the g -th gene, let $\mathbf{Y}_g = (Y_{1g}, \dots, Y_{Ig})^T$, $\mathbf{n}_g = (n_{1g}, \dots, n_{Ig})^T$, $\phi_{g:I \times 1} = (\phi_g, \dots, \phi_g)^T$, $\beta_g = (\beta_{1g}, \dots, \beta_{Kg})^T$, and $\mathbf{X}_{I \times K}$ be the design matrix as defined previously. Furthermore, let $\ell(\beta_g)$ denote the log-prior of β_g , $\ell(\mathbf{Y}_g | \beta_g)$ denote the log-likelihood of \mathbf{Y}_g , and $\ell(\beta_g | \mathbf{Y}_g)$ denote the log-posterior of β_g . For the below notation, we abandon the ‘g’ subscript for simplicity. Then it can be shown that:

$$\begin{aligned}
\ell(\boldsymbol{\beta}) &\propto \log(\beta_j^2/\gamma_j^2 + 1) + \frac{1}{2\sigma^2} \sum_{j' \neq j} \beta_{j'}^2, \\
\ell(\mathbf{Y}|\boldsymbol{\beta}) &\propto \text{sum} \left\{ \log \left[\Gamma \left(\mathbf{n} - \mathbf{Y} + \boldsymbol{\phi} - \frac{\boldsymbol{\phi}}{1 + \exp(-\mathbf{X}\boldsymbol{\beta})} \right) \right] \right. \\
&\quad + \log \left[\Gamma \left(\mathbf{Y} + \frac{\boldsymbol{\phi}}{1 + \exp(-\mathbf{X}\boldsymbol{\beta})} \right) \right] \\
&\quad - \log \left[\Gamma \left(\boldsymbol{\phi} - \frac{\boldsymbol{\phi}}{1 + \exp(-\mathbf{X}\boldsymbol{\beta})} \right) \right] \\
&\quad \left. - \log \left[\Gamma \left(\frac{\boldsymbol{\phi}}{1 + \exp(-\mathbf{X}\boldsymbol{\beta})} \right) \right] \right\} \\
\ell(\boldsymbol{\beta}|\mathbf{Y}) &\propto \ell(\boldsymbol{\beta}) + \ell(\mathbf{Y}|\boldsymbol{\beta})
\end{aligned}$$

The logarithmic, gamma, division and summation operations are element-wise operations. For instance, if $\mathbf{X} = [x_{ij}]$, then $\log \mathbf{X} = [\log x_{ij}]$, $\Gamma(\mathbf{X}) = [\Gamma(x_{ij})]$, $\mathbf{1}/\mathbf{X} = [1/x_{ij}]$ and $\text{sum}(\mathbf{X}) = \sum_i \sum_j x_{ij}$. The term on the left side of $\ell(\boldsymbol{\beta})$ is the log-prior assumed by apeglm for the coefficient we wish to shrink and the summation term on the right side is the log-prior of the non-shrunk coefficients introduced for numerical stability. Furthermore, one can show that:

$$\begin{aligned}
\ell'(\boldsymbol{\beta}) &= \left(\frac{\beta_1}{\sigma^2}, \dots, \frac{\beta_{j-1}}{\sigma^2}, \frac{2\beta_j}{\gamma^2 + \beta_j^2}, \frac{\beta_{j+1}}{\sigma^2}, \dots, \frac{\beta_K}{\sigma^2} \right)^T \\
\ell'(\mathbf{Y}|\boldsymbol{\beta}) &= \mathbf{X}^T \left[\frac{\boldsymbol{\phi} \exp(-\mathbf{X}\boldsymbol{\beta})}{(1 + \exp(-\mathbf{X}\boldsymbol{\beta}))^{\circ 2}} \circ \left\{ \psi \left(\mathbf{n} - \mathbf{Y} + \boldsymbol{\phi} - \frac{\boldsymbol{\phi}}{1 + \exp(-\mathbf{X}\boldsymbol{\beta})} \right) \right. \right. \\
&\quad - \psi \left(\mathbf{Y} + \frac{\boldsymbol{\phi}}{1 + \exp(-\mathbf{X}\boldsymbol{\beta})} \right) \\
&\quad - \psi \left(\boldsymbol{\phi} - \frac{\boldsymbol{\phi}}{1 + \exp(-\mathbf{X}\boldsymbol{\beta})} \right) \\
&\quad \left. \left. + \psi \left(\frac{\boldsymbol{\phi}}{1 + \exp(-\mathbf{X}\boldsymbol{\beta})} \right) \right\} \right] \\
\ell'(\boldsymbol{\beta}|\mathbf{Y}) &= \ell'(\boldsymbol{\beta}) + \ell'(\mathbf{Y}|\boldsymbol{\beta})
\end{aligned}$$

where $\ell'(\boldsymbol{\beta})$, $\ell'(\mathbf{Y}|\boldsymbol{\beta})$, $\ell'(\boldsymbol{\beta}|\mathbf{Y})$ denote the gradient vectors of the log-prior, log-likelihood and log-posterior, respectively, $\mathbf{X} \circ \mathbf{Y}$ denotes element-wise multiplication of matrices X and Y, $\mathbf{X}^{\circ n}$ denotes the nth element-wise power of matrix X, division is element-wise as before, and ψ denotes element-wise operation of the digamma function. Using the above log-posterior and gradient vector, we estimate the mode of the log-posterior in C++ with the L-BFGS algorithm (Nocedal 1980) implemented within the `LFBFGS++` and `RcppNumerical` libraries (Qiu et. al. 2018). The covariance matrix of our estimates is based on a Laplace approximation of the posterior, or the asymptotic normality of the posterior mode. Specifically, the covariance matrix is estimated as the negative inverted Hessian, which is based on the coefficient estimates calculated in C++ as well as the closed-form log posterior and gradient vector above, and is computed using the `optimHess` function in R.

For ML estimation, we just assume the same wide normal prior for all predictors, and the resulting changes to the log posterior and gradient of the log posterior are straightforward.

Estimating Overdispersion while Coefficients are Fixed

The steps below are executed in iteration steps 2, 4 and 6 above and assume that coefficients are fixed and known. All computations are performed in R, and thus all referenced packaged and functions are R packages

and functions.

The likelihood for the overdispersion parameter of the g th gene, ϕ_g , can be written as:

$$\ell(\phi_g) = \sum_i \frac{\binom{n_{ig}}{Y_{ig}} B(Y_{ig} + \phi_g p_{ig}, n_{ig} - Y_{ig} + \phi_g(1 - p_{ig}))}{B(\phi_g p_{ig}, \phi_g(1 - p_{ig}))}$$

where n_{ig} , Y_{ig} and $p_{ig} = [1 + \exp(-\mathbf{x}_i^T \boldsymbol{\beta}_g)]^{-1}$ were all defined in the ‘‘Model Setup’’ section. This is the summation of the beta-binomial mass function as parametrized in (1), evaluated at each sample. The mass function for the beta-binomial is calculated using the `emdbook` library (Bolker 2019). Though the theoretical parameter space of ϕ_g is the open interval $(0, \infty)$, constrained optimization of the log-likelihood is performed using Brent’s line search implemented via the `optimize` function (Brent 1973) with a default minimum overdispersion parameter estimate of 0.01 and a maximum estimate of 5000. The lower constraint is used for numerical stability as the evaluated density is degenerate for $\phi_g = 0$, and the upper constraint is used so that genes with no overdispersion do not have infinite estimated values of ϕ_g .

We found that setting the maximum estimate of ϕ_g beyond 5000 did not lead to meaningful differences in the coefficient estimates. This is because as $\phi_g \rightarrow \infty$, the beta-binomial distribution converges to the binomial distribution (Gupta and Nadarajah 2004). With $\phi_g = 5000$, the ML estimate of $\boldsymbol{\beta}_g$ is usually already so close to the binomial ML estimate of $\boldsymbol{\beta}_g$ that letting ϕ_g be any larger won’t meaningfully change the ML estimate. However, the package does allow the maximum (as well as the minimum) to be changed by the user if desired. For example, in the estimation performance benchmarks in the main paper we set the minimum and maximum at 1 and 500, and widening the range did not meaningfully change any results.

Estimating the Scale of the Cauchy Prior

The steps below are executed in iteration step 6b for calculating `apeglm` estimates in step 7. All computations are performed in R, and thus all referenced packaged and functions are R packages and functions.

The Cauchy prior in the `apeglm` model is estimated empirically by pooling information across genes. We require an initial vector of ML estimates and their standard errors. Here we take the ML estimates $\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_j^{(3)} = (\hat{\beta}_{j1}^{(5)}, \dots, \hat{\beta}_{jG}^{(5)})^T$ calculated in the previous iteration (iteration step 5), and treat their estimated standard errors $\sigma(\hat{\beta}_{jg}^{(5)})$, $1 \leq g \leq G$ as the true standard errors (estimation of the standard errors is based on the limiting normal distribution of the MLE). For the below notation, we abandon the ‘(5)’ superscript for notational simplicity. We then adapt the scale of the prior to the MLEs by solving the following equation:

$$S^2 = \sum_{g=1}^G (\hat{\beta}_{jg}^2 - \sigma^2(\hat{\beta}_{jg})) I_g(S^2) / \sum_{g=1}^G I_g(S^2)$$

where $I_g(a) = \frac{1}{2(a + \sigma^2(\hat{\beta}_{jg}))^2}$. S^2 is an empirical Bayes estimate of the variance of the posterior normal distribution for β_{jg} generated by assuming $\hat{\beta}_{jg} | \beta_{jg} \stackrel{ind}{\sim} N(\beta_{jg}, \sigma^2(\beta_{jg}))$ and $\beta_{jg} \stackrel{iid}{\sim} N(0, S^2)$ for $1 \leq g \leq G$, and was derived in Efron and Morris 1975. Although a Cauchy prior is actually used for the coefficients in $\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_j$, and although we do not actually know the true standard errors, the original authors for `apeglm` found that setting the scale of the prior under the working assumptions that the true prior is normal and that the estimated standard errors are the true standard errors worked well in practice, and we do not consider making any adjustments here. The equation is solved using Brent’s line search in R (Brent 1973).

Additional Technical Steps

Elements of the vector $\exp(-\mathbf{X}\boldsymbol{\beta})$ are capped between 0.001 and 999 when calculating $\ell(\mathbf{Y}|\boldsymbol{\beta})$ and $\ell'(\mathbf{Y}|\boldsymbol{\beta})$ to prevent calculations from becoming larger than what C++ double precision can handle and to prevent non-finite estimates and convergence issues in cases of complete separation. For the same reason, numerical variables are recommended to be standardized by the user to have mean 0 and variance 1. A linear

transformation of the log-posterior is applied to prevent it from being too large or approaching too closely to zero. This improves computational performance and helps prevent convergence problems for our given posterior. When estimating overdispersion, the `optimize` function is technically used to estimate the MLE of $\log(\theta_g)$, which is then exponentiated to estimate the MLE of θ_g . The log-likelihood is more symmetrical with respect to $\log(\theta_g)$, which makes R’s `optimize` function perform better, and it also makes it easier to optimize over a larger range of θ_g . When running the `optim_lbfgs` function in C++ from the `RcppNumerical` library, we set `eps_f` to 1e-12 and `eps_g` to 1e-10 to control for the small relative movement in our posterior during convergence. The full source code for the `apeglm` package is available [here](#) and a vignette explaining how to use the package for modelling ASRe counts is available [here](#).

Evaluating Numerical Accuracy

We compare the numerical accuracy of our method against the same packages used for the computational comparisons in the main paper, and with the same simulation as that used for the computational comparisons. To recap, we simulate $\mathbf{Y}_{5000 \times 100} = [Y_{ij}]$ from $\text{BetaBin}(n_{ij}, p_i, \phi_i)$, $\boldsymbol{\phi} = (\phi_1, \dots, \phi_{5000})^T$ from $U(1, 1000)$, $\mathbf{p} = (p_1, \dots, p_{5000})$ from $N(.5, .05)$ and $\mathbf{N}_{5000 \times 100} = [n_{ij}]$ from $\text{NB}(\mu_i, 1/\theta_i)$, where $\boldsymbol{\mu} = (\mu_1, \dots, \mu_{5000})$, $\boldsymbol{\theta} = (\theta_1, \dots, \theta_{5000})$ are based on DESeq2 estimates (Love, Huber and Anders 2014) from the `airway` dataset (Himes et. al. 2014). More details can be found in the original paper (Zitovsky and Love 2019) and [vignette](#). \mathbf{Y} and \mathbf{N} are 5000 gene by 100 sample matrices of simulated allele-specific and total counts for one of two alleles. It is assumed that all 100 samples have the same two alleles for all 5000 genes. We then split the samples into two groups randomly. The design matrix is thus $\mathbf{X}_{100 \times 2} = (\mathbf{1}, \mathbf{x}_2)$ where $\mathbf{1} = (1, 1, \dots, 1)^T$ is a 100 length vector of ones and $\mathbf{x}_2 = (1, 0, 1, 0, \dots, 1, 0)^T$ is an indicator function for the second group. Six packages were considered: `VGAM`, `HRQoL`, `gamlss`, `aods3` and `aod`. Of these packages, only `VGAM` and `aod` was able to model all 5000 genes, with the other packages failing to converge or throwing errors with somewhat high frequency. Thus these are the only two packages that will be used in the comparison.

We are primarily interested in the numerical accuracy of the regression coefficient estimates, with the overdispersion seen to us as a nuisance parameter. If we compare the likelihoods of the packages directly, the question of which yields more accurate regression coefficient estimates will be confounded with differences in overdispersion. Moreover, our package constrains optimization of overdispersion to be in the interval $(0.01, 5000)$, and while this constraint doesn’t impact estimation of the regression coefficients (as we will show shortly), it can lead to lower likelihoods. One possible remedy would be to search over a much larger range, say $(0.0001, 1, 000, 000)$. However, as the overdispersion estimates by all three packages tended to strongly agree anyway, we thought it better to just compute `apeglm` likelihoods with `apeglm` regression coefficient estimates and `aod` overdispersion estimates when comparing likelihoods to that to the `aod` package. Moreover, we computed `apeglm` likelihoods with `apeglm` regression coefficient estimates and `VGAM` overdispersion estimates when comparing to the `VGAM` package. Though this might slightly bias results in favor of the other packages, it will allow us to control for overdispersion and focus on numerical accuracy of estimating the regression coefficients. Moreover, we increased the variance of the imposed large-scale normal prior from 15^2 to 1000^2 . Otherwise, this prior will shrink estimates away from the global likelihood, and the numerical accuracy of our method will be confounded with a conscious choice to shrink finitely large estimates. We investigate the impact of using the default prior variance 15^2 later on.

The log-likelihood of the beta-binomial is unstable in that very small differences in estimates (e.g. < 0.001) can lead to very large differences in log-likelihood (e.g. > 100), and vice-versa for large differences in estimates. This lack of smoothness is due to the fact that the beta-binomial density consists of fractions of complex indefinite integrals. Therefore, looking at which method gives higher likelihood in absolute terms (e.g. by plotting boxplots of the differences in likelihood) would not be very informative, as the seemingly large differences in likelihood could correspond to meaningless differences in the estimates. We felt that a better method to assess numerical accuracy is to look for genes such that differences in the estimates between the methods is non-negligible, and for those genes observe which package gives estimates with larger relative likelihood. We consider differences in regression coefficient estimates to be negligible if their Euclidean distance is less than 0.01. Table 1 shows the difference between `apeglm` and `aod` log-likelihood among regression coefficients whose Euclidean distance exceeded 0.01, and Table 2 shows such differences between `apeglm` and `VGAM`.

Table 1: **Non-Negligible Differences in apeg1m and aod Estimates for the 100 Sample Simulation.**

$\ \widehat{\beta}^{(\text{apeglm})} - \widehat{\beta}^{(\text{aod})}\ $	$\mathcal{LL}^{(\text{apeglm})} - \mathcal{LL}^{(\text{aod})}$	$\ \widehat{\beta}^{(\text{apeglm})} - \widehat{\beta}^{(\text{aod})}\ $	$\mathcal{LL}^{(\text{apeglm})} - \mathcal{LL}^{(\text{aod})}$
0.046	0.8	0.015	2.561
0.045	0.906	0.015	0.402
0.044	0.942	0.014	0.134
0.024	0.802	0.014	1.58
0.024	2.553	0.013	0.104
0.023	0.633	0.013	0.257
0.023	2.344	0.013	1.789
0.021	0.392	0.013	0.108
0.021	0.739	0.012	0.558
0.020	2.218	0.012	0.502
0.020	2.719	0.012	0.608
0.020	0.183	0.012	0.553
0.019	1.728	0.012	0.244
0.018	0.684	0.012	0.142
0.018	1.03	0.011	0.041
0.018	0.161	0.011	0.53
0.017	2.351	0.011	0.118
0.017	14.495	0.011	0.445
0.016	0.826	0.011	1.067
0.016	1.327	0.011	0.608
0.016	0.94	0.011	0.264
0.016	4.907	0.010	0.529

Table 2: **Non-Negligible Differences in apeg1m and VGAM Estimates for the 100 Sample Simulation.**

$\ \widehat{\beta}^{(\text{apeglm})} - \widehat{\beta}^{(\text{VGAM})}\ $	$\mathcal{LL}^{(\text{apeglm})} - \mathcal{LL}^{(\text{VGAM})}$
0.015	0.017

Among all genes such that the differences between the packages were non-negligible, the estimates from `apeglm` were always closer to the global maximum of the likelihood than `aod`. Differences between `apeglm` and `VGAM` were smaller, with the largest Euclidean distance between the packages being only 0.015. However, for what it is worth, it was the `apeglm` estimate that was closer to the global maximum.

For the previous simulation, the sample size is large, the true group effect sizes are all zero and the overdispersion is not extreme. To shake things up, we reduce sample size to 20. We also spike in allelic imbalance of $p = 0.75$ for the second group and extreme values of ϕ alternating between 0.1 and 500,000, for the first 100 genes. There were several genes with true overdispersion 0.1 where `aod` failed to converge. The package gave seemingly infinite values of the effect size estimates associated with log-likelihoods of negative infinity, even though the true MLEs of these estimates was not infinite. Thus only `VGAM` was considered for this simulation. Table 3 shows the differences in log-likelihood for the `apeglm` and `VGAM` regression coefficients with non-negligible differences among the first 200 genes. Again differences between `VGAM` and `apeglm` were small, with the largest Euclidean difference between the estimates only 0.02. `apeglm` was more numerically accurate on average, though to be fair, these differences are not large enough to matter. Moreover, by increasing the number of times we iterate between estimation of β and ϕ , we could make `apeglm` more numerically accurate than `VGAM` across all genes universally, though we don't think its really worth the extra computation.

Recall that we are using an uninformative normal prior on our coefficients with variance 1000² to focus on our package's numerical accuracy. What happens if we use the default prior variance 15²? We can see from Table 4 that for genes with very large MLEs, the estimated coefficients are shrunk towards zero from the global maximum, and thus `VGAM`'s estimates are closer to the global maximum of the observed log-likelihood. However, our estimates are actually closer to the truth than `VGAM` (the true regression parameters are $\beta_0 = 0.5$

Table 3: **Non-Negligible Differences in apeg1m and VGAM Estimates for the 20 Sample Simulation.**

$\ \widehat{\beta}^{(\text{apeg1m})} - \widehat{\beta}^{(\text{VGAM})}\ $	$\mathcal{LL}^{(\text{apeg1m})} - \mathcal{LL}^{(\text{VGAM})}$
0.02	0.004
0.02	0.003
0.01	-0.0002

Table 4: **Top 5 Differences in apeg1m and VGAM Estimates with apeg1m’s Default Normal Prior.**

$\widehat{\beta}_0^{(\text{apeg1m})}$ and $\widehat{\beta}_1^{(\text{apeg1m})}$ are the estimated intercept and group 2 effect for our beta-binomial logistic regression model according to apeg1m, and similarly for $\widehat{\beta}_0^{(\text{VGAM})}$ and $\widehat{\beta}_1^{(\text{VGAM})}$

$\ \widehat{\beta}^{(\text{apeg1m})} - \widehat{\beta}^{(\text{VGAM})}\ $	$\mathcal{LL}^{(\text{apeg1m})} - \mathcal{LL}^{(\text{VGAM})}$	$\widehat{\beta}_0^{(\text{apeg1m})}$	$\widehat{\beta}_1^{(\text{apeg1m})}$	$\widehat{\beta}_0^{(\text{VGAM})}$	$\widehat{\beta}_1^{(\text{VGAM})}$
1.118	-1.009	-0.025	7.193	-0.042	8.311
0.028	-0.0004	0.273	5.704	0.272	5.732
0.027	-0.0003	0.078	5.31	0.076	5.337
0.026	-0.0003	-0.14	5.441	-0.141	5.467
0.022	-0.0002	-0.074	4.114	-0.076	4.136

and $\beta_1 = 0.75$). When there is very large numerical instability in the likelihood (e.g. due to near-separability, small sample size and/or high overdispersion) and the resulting ML estimates are extremely large, the true effect sizes are almost always lower than the estimated values. Moreover, in this case, even if they weren’t closer to the truth, the difference in the underlying group-specific allelic proportion estimates would be meaningless. For instance, for the gene with the most shrinkage exhibited (first row of Table 4), the allelic proportion for group 2 is estimated as 0.9997 by the VGAM package and 0.9992 by the apeg1m package. For the 100 sample simulation, all differences in estimates from using the default prior and using our non-informative prior (normal with variance 1000²) are negligible. This is because the default prior only becomes informative when the maximum of the log-likelihood is very large (e.g. > 5) and the information is very low, and for the first simulation the sample size is not too small and the MLEs are all below 1. Gelman et. al. 2008 argue for wide zero-centered priors on GLM coefficients with a logistic link as a default for routine applied use, and such is the default in many Bayesian and non-Bayesian regression packages. We defer the numerous computational, numerical and generalization advantages of this prior to the paper. Though such a prior seldom hurts more than it helps, those who wish to not employ this prior can do so by setting the scale of the normal prior to a very large value, such as 1000.

We can conclude that apeg1m is more numerically accurate and reliable than all other packages considered. VGAM has the closest numerical accuracy to apeg1m, and it was also the only package (other than apeg1m) to always converge. However, VGAM also takes many times longer than even the non-apeg1m packages and still does not exceed the numerical accuracy of apeg1m. In fact, while VGAM only took about 80 times longer than apeg1m for the gene used in Figure 6 in the main paper, for many genes VGAM actually took hundreds of times longer than apeg1m. These comparison times also only apply when the design matrix consists of an intercept and a single binary variable, and for more complex design matrices, the difference in computation between VGAM and apeg1m is likely to widen (see Figure 7 in the main paper). The convergence status and log-likelihood for apeg1m estimates was also investigated for various other simulations and data sets, including the standard normal and student’s t simulations and various subsets of the mice dataset discussed in the main paper, and when the ML estimate exists the apeg1m package converged 100% of the time to a maximum. Even when the data is completely separable, the bounds on the sample-specific probability estimates to values very slightly above 0 and very slightly below 1 and the wide normal prior will guarantee convergence to a meaningful finite solution (meaningful in that the finite solution is allowed to get larger as the sample size and total counts increase). Finally, it is worth noting that although we have focused here on numerical accuracy of the regression coefficients, apeg1m is also numerically accurate if accurate estimation of the overdispersion is also of interest. Because we maximize with respect to $\log(\phi)$ first and then exponentiate to get ϕ , our package can handle extremely large ranges of ϕ for the search procedure without many convergence problems or much computational burden, if one is interested in accurate estimation of ϕ outside the (0.01, 5000) range.